

1 **Accepted version – Nutrition Bulletin, July 2025**

2 **Microbial Protein for Human Consumption: Towards sustainable protein production**

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10 Keywords. microbial protein, sustainability, fermentation, digestibility, consumer acceptance

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13 **Abstract**

14 Protein from animal sources significantly contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, driving the need
15 for sustainable alternative protein sources to meet global dietary demands while reducing
16 environmental impact. This project explores microbial protein, derived through cellular agriculture
17 using fermentation technology, as a viable, sustainable, and high-quality protein for human
18 consumption. This report describes a multidisciplinary approach to assessing the feasibility of
19 incorporating microbial protein into human food systems, guided by four key objectives. First, a market
20 analysis to identify opportunities and challenges for incorporating microbial protein into existing food
21 products, assessing its potential to improve the protein quality of plant-based foods. Second, the
22 project will evaluate the protein quality and digestibility of reformulated products using advanced
23 models simulating human gastrointestinal processes. Third, consumer perceptions and barriers to
24 adopting bacterial-based proteins will be investigated, addressing safety, health, and sustainability
25 concerns. Overall findings will inform the development of a technical document outlining actionable
26 recommendations for commercialising microbial proteins as food ingredients.

27 This multidisciplinary project aims to support the sustainable diversification of dietary protein sources,
28 contributing to global efforts toward achieving sustainable food systems. The project is funded by the
29 Start Healthy, Stay Healthy (STAR) Hub, a Diet and Health Open Innovation Research Club (OIRC) which
30 is funded by the UK Research & Innovation (UKRI) Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research
31 Council (BBSRC).

32

33 **Introduction**

34 Protein derived from animal products is a major factor in greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) with an
35 estimated 57% of GHG from food production coming from animal-based agriculture (Xu et al., 2021).
36 There is also an acknowledgement that the intensification of commodity production, such as soybean,
37 in recent decades has resulted in significant socioeconomic and environmental consequences
38 including intensified land use, deforestation, and interconnected (peri-coupled) socioeconomic
39 impacts (da Silva et al., 2021). The pursuit of alternative proteins is one of the key areas of focus of the
40 Food and Agriculture Organisations's (FAO) Programme Priority Area on Bioeconomy for Sustainable

41 Food and Agriculture which aims to support the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal target
42 12.2 – Sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources. There is a recognition that if
43 we are to sustainably provide sufficient protein for the global population, we need to diversify available
44 sources of dietary protein and become less reliant on animal-derived protein.

45 These climate factors along with animal welfare concerns are nudging consumers to source alternative
46 protein food options in a way that has driven the UK market for non-animal derived alternatives to a
47 value of £942 million in 2023 (GFI-Europe, 2024).

48 This drive towards a shift from “conventional animal” protein sources to alternative sources has
49 created space for products such as plant-based meat and milk alternatives (Smith et al., 2024).
50 Interestingly, hybrid products which contain both animal and plant-based proteins in an attempt to
51 improve the sustainability of traditional animal-based products are also becoming available for the
52 flexitarian market. In general, plant-based animal alternatives are of lower protein quality than their
53 animal counterparts. This is generally attributed to an incomplete amino acid profile with plant-based
54 protein generally being lower in essential amino acids such as methionine and lysine (Young & Pellett,
55 1994) and/or reduced digestibility and net protein utilisation due to interactions with other
56 components within the foods such as fibre and polyphenolic compounds such as tannins (Cirkovic
57 Velickovic & Stanic-Vucinic, 2018; Sarwar Gilani, Wu Xiao, & Cockell, 2012). It must however be
58 acknowledged that considerable research and development has been undertaken in the area of plant-
59 based meat alternatives combine different plant sources of protein with complementary EAA profiles
60 to improve levels of limiting amino acids and improve the protein chemical score of the foods.
61 However, the appearance of EAAs in human plasma after ingestion of such foods is still generally lower
62 than that of their meat alternatives (Pham et al., 2022).

63 Emerging technologies and consumer demand have created an environment for new novel alternative
64 proteins to be conceptualised, researched, and in some cases commercialised. The most successful of
65 these is mycoprotein which was developed and commercialised by Quorn in the UK in the 1980s. This
66 research area has developed considerably with the emergence of lab-grown muscle protein and
67 cellular agriculture such as bacteria produced through fermentation.

68 Cellular agriculture utilises fermentation technology to grow bacteria such as *Methylococcus*
69 *capsulatus* that convert carbon and energy into high-quality, non-GMO protein sources. The product
70 is produced in bioreactors which allows production at scale using very little water and agricultural land
71 compared to conventional agriculture (Pikaar et al., 2018), to create sustainable, traceable and
72 affordable protein (see figure 1). Importantly the microbes convert nitrogen into cellular proteins with
73 an efficiency close to 100% (Pikaar et al., 2017) with the resulting microbial proteins constituting
74 greater than 70% of the dry biomass weight (Oba et al., 2023) producing an estimated 4.6kg of CO₂
75 per kg of final product. In comparison, in the UK, the CO₂ equivalent per kg of product produced is
76 conservatively estimated at 17.12kg for beef and 14.6kg for sheep (AHDB, 2010) and the global median
77 for soybean production is estimated to be 2kg (Poore & Nemecek, 2018)

78 The amino acid profile of the microbial protein is excellent with all essential amino acids present in
79 good quantities and a digestibility of >85% in animal models (Oba et al., 2023). The high quality of the
80 microbial protein gives potential for use in mixed protein source products and could be used to
81 improve the protein quality of food formulations such as plant-based meat alternatives and ready to
82 eat foods and milks which have overall poor protein quantity and quality where one or more essential
83 amino acid is limiting.

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86 Figure 1 – Microbial protein production

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88 The project described here aims to explore the feasibility of using bacterial protein as a food
89 ingredient; and inform the next steps needed to commercialise the protein product in the human food
90 market.

91 The project is funded by the Start Healthy, Stay Healthy (STAR) Hub, a Diet and Health Open Innovation
92 Research Club (OIRC) innovation hub which is funded by the UK Research & Innovation (UKRI)
93 Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC). OIRC promotes collaborations
94 between industry and academia in order foster interdisciplinary partnerships to accelerate research
95 translation, support sustainable food systems, and enable healthier lifestyles across all stages of life
96 (<https://oirc.org.uk/>). The project will run for 15 months (August 2024–November 2025) and has four
97 key objectives related to the development and dissemination of guidelines for the formulation of
98 palatable, cost-effective, higher-protein foods which incorporate microbial protein produced by
99 Calysta UK Ltd.

100 **Objective one: Conduct a market assessment to describe current trends in non-animal-based protein**
101 **products, with the goal of informing the development of reformulated foods that incorporate**
102 **microbial proteins.**

103 The UK plant-based food market was estimated to be worth £942 million in 2024. The market
104 decreased overall by 2.8% between 2022 and 2023 but there are key segments of the market which
105 are still in growth, including cheese, cream and milks (GFI-Europe, 2024). There are analogues made
106 using soybean which have good amino acid profiles (Kudęłka, Kowalska, & Popis, 2021) and a Digestible
107 Indispensable Amino Acid Score (DIAAS) of 90 (van den Berg et al., 2022), however, many of the
108 products now available, such as market leading milk and yoghurt alternatives are produced using
109 grains such as oats (Yu et al., 2023) almonds or rice (Pucci et al., 2024) which have a lower quality
110 amino acid profile when compared to their animal derived counterparts. This provides an opportunity
111 to create hybrid products with bacterial protein added to create non-animal derived products with
112 good protein quantity and quality. This objective comprises two components:

113 i. Market analysis

114 Market analysis will focus on identifying the opportunities, challenges, and strategies for including
115 microbial protein within existing products. Using the most up to date market data, key segments of
116 interest will be identified and key products within those segments will be chosen for development.
117 Literature will be reviewed to allow us to choose those foods which would most benefit from the
118 inclusion of microbial protein. This will include considerations of key product categories and consumer
119 segments as well as potential for protein quality improvements.

120 ii. Product development

121 Foods selected through the market analysis will undergo reformulation using total protein and protein
122 chemical score calculations as guiding metrics. Desk based calculations based on essential amino acid
123 profiles of the chosen products from published literature will be included. Chemical scores will be
124 estimated based on published amino acid profiles before and after the addition of the microbial
125 protein based on the recommendations by WHO 2013. The products will be formulated based on UK
126 food regulations of “a source of protein” (protein as 12% or more of total energy) and “high in protein”
127 (protein as 20% or more of total energy). Products will be prepared, including cooking where
128 necessary, and assessed in a Digestible Indispensable Amino Acid Score (DIAAS) like gut model.

129 **Objective Two – Assessment of protein quality and digestibility**

130 The gold standard for the measurement of quality and digestibility of protein in foods is through DIAAS.
131 DIAAS which measures the digestibility of protein at the end of the small intestine requires a growing
132 pig to be fed and harvested for the assessment to be conducted. There is a growing call within the
133 scientific community for models to be produced to allow DIAAS to be assessed through laboratory-
134 based methods instead of animals. Aelius Biotech Ltd has developed a proprietary model of the human
135 gastrointestinal tract that enables the study of various products, including foods, functional foods,
136 nutraceuticals, formulations, and pharmaceuticals, and their interactions within the digestive system.
137 This advanced model integrates digestion and absorption in a single system using a patented mucus
138 layer. This innovation transforms any 2D cell culture system into a 3D model that accurately simulates
139 digestion and absorption (Chater, 2023).

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141 The Human Gastrointestinal Model provides detailed insights into how products behave in the
142 digestive system. The model is particularly useful for assessing protein quality, offering measurements
143 like DIAAS. This score evaluates protein quality based on its true ileal digestibility. The system not only
144 calculates the DIAAS and provides a detailed amino acid profile but also tracks digestion rates over
145 time throughout the digestive tract.

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147 This work package will utilise the Aelius biotech model to understand the quality and digestibility of
148 the proteins in products created in objective one.

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150 **Objective Three: Understand the consumer perceptions and barriers to consuming bacteria-based**
151 **proteins.**

152 Recent consumer perceptions report into alternative proteins by the European Institute of Innovation
153 and Technology (2023) found that there are three key consumer segments with differing perspectives
154 on protein. These are “meat lovers”, “plant purists” and “omnivores”. It was reported that meat lovers
155 and plant purists hold positive opinions about their protein food segments and the group which has
156 the greatest potential for alternative proteins to be positioned are omnivores. However, some
157 misconceptions need to be clarified around safety, benefits to health, and environmental sustainability.
158 Similar findings were reported by the UK Food Standards Agency, where safety concerns were
159 identified as a key barrier to consuming insect-based or lab-grown proteins. In regard to encouraging
160 uptake, 42% of respondents reported that nothing could encourage them to try lab grown meat, but
161 27% could be persuaded if they knew it was safe to eat, and 23% if they trusted that it was properly
162 regulated (Ibrahim Jarchlo, 2022). These findings from Europe and the UK highlight that some of the
163 consumer perceptions of alternative proteins involve major concerns around safety and healthiness of
164 insects or lab grown proteins. To our knowledge, there are no reports which aim to gauge consumer
165 perceptions of fermented bacterial based proteins. The overall aim of this work package is to explore
166 consumer perceptions surrounding microbial protein, to gauge the likelihood of future inclusion into
167 their diet.

168 This work package will involve an explanatory sequential mixed methods design. The quantitative
169 phase will involve conducting a cross-sectional survey among a UK-representative sample to
170 understand the behavioural factors influencing consumer acceptance of incorporating bacterial
171 protein into a diet. This will also include how use of semantics may influence uptake. Relevant
172 frameworks, such as The Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF) (Atkins et al., 2017) and the
173 Theoretical Framework of Acceptability (TFA) (Sekhon, Cartwright, & Francis, 2017) will be used to
174 guide development of survey items. Survey data will be analysed using appropriate statistical methods
175 and will inform the qualitative phase of the work package, through development of a semi-structured
176 topic guide for use in a series of focus groups. The aim of this phase is to examine the behavioural

177 influences in further depth, alongside prospective acceptability of the products developed within WP
178 1-2. This phase aims to recruit a diverse sample of participants, to aid generalisability of results to the
179 wider UK population. Template analysis will then be used aid interpretation of focus group data,
180 involving the development of a coding template with inductive and deductive themes.

181

182 **Objective Four: Collate project findings to produce a technical document**

183 Building on outcomes one, two and three academic and industry stakeholders will create a document
184 that outlines the efficacy and feasibility of producing food-safe versions of Calista's proteins. The
185 document will integrate experimental results, market analysis, and consumer insights to outline the
186 potential of microbial proteins as a sustainable and high-quality food ingredient. It will also provide
187 actionable recommendations for the commercialisation and regulatory approval of these proteins.

188 **Conclusion**

189 The Microbial Protein for Human Consumption project will use a multidisciplinary approach to provide
190 an evidence base for the use of microbial protein in human food systems. The project will provide
191 valuable information on the efficacy of reformulating products using microbial protein to improve the
192 protein quality of commonly consumed foods and the barriers and opportunities for their
193 commercialisation.

194

195 **Author contributions**

196 Anthony Watson, Rebecca Townsend and Matt Longshaw all contributed equally to the writing and
197 preparation of the manuscript.

198 Academic team: Dr Anthony Watson, Newcastle University (Principal Investigator); Dr Rebecca
199 Townsend, Newcastle University (Co-Investigator); Dr Matt Longshaw, Calysta UK (Co-Investigator).

200 **Funding**

201 This study was funded by the Star Hub Surrey - a Diet and Health Open Innovation Research Club (OIRC)
202 innovation hub, a network funded by the UK Research & Innovation (UKRI) Biotechnology and
203 Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) that promotes collaborations between industry and
204 academia (Project Number: FA1_23-12).

205 **Conflict of interest**

206 Matt Longshaw is an employee of Calysta UK Ltd who have made an in-kind contribution to the project.
207 Anthony Watson has in the past received funding from the food industry and has received financial
208 compensation for non-food industry facing consultancy. Rebecca Townsend declares no conflicts of
209 interest.

210 **Data Availability**

211 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author
212 upon reasonable request.

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